

Kalaignar M. Karunanidhi played a vital role in the growth of the Dravidian Movement in Tamil Nadu

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Abstract

The political career and contributions of M. Karunanidhi, a prominent leader of the Dravidian movement and the Dravida Munnetra Kazhagam (DMK). After succeeding C. N. Annadurai in 1969, Karunanidhi focused on industrialization, educational expansion, and social welfare. His government introduced free education up to the pre-university level, supported farmers through land reforms, and improved living conditions for the poor through housing schemes. During his second term, he implemented major initiatives such as the Slum Clearance Board, nationalization of transport services, and pension schemes for aided college teachers. He also advocated state autonomy and played a significant role in establishing the right of Chief Ministers to hoist the national flag on Independence Day. His opposition to the Indian Emergency led to the dismissal of his government. Karunanidhi served five terms as Chief Minister and contributed significantly to Tamil literature and cinema. His political ideology was influenced by Annadurai's principles of secularism, social justice, and linguistic pride. Both leaders emphasized democracy, opposed religious politics, and promoted Tamil identity within Indian unity. Karunanidhi remains a key figure in Tamil Nadu's political history for his long public service and commitment to social reform.

Keywords: Kalaignar M. Karunanidhi, Liberty, Dravidian ideology, Egocentrism, Equality, Social Justice, Tamil Culture, Identity

INTRODUCTION

The First term of office of the Chief Minister M. Karunanidhi was from 10th February 1969 to 15th March 1971. Indeed, M. Karunanidhi succeeded C.N. Annadurai and had to **consolidate** his position. He was interested in the industrialization of Tamil Nadu. He made sure that the Salem steel mill was to be founded by then Prime Minister, Indira Gandhi. Primary importance was given to the expansion of education. Free education was provided to students up to the pre-university course in colleges. The midday meals continued in the schools. Karunanidhi was always been concerned with the welfare of farmers. He reduced land ownership to 15 standard acres. Manomaniam Per. Sundaranar's song "Neeraarum Kadaluduttha" became the prayer song at government functions.

The Chief Minister term of M. Karunanidhi

The Second Chief Minister term of M. Karunanidhi was from 15th March 1971 to 31st January 1976. Karunanidhi served as Chief Minister for nearly 59 months during his second term. In the general election of March 1971, his party, the D.M.K., won 184 seats in the Legislative Assembly of Tamil Nadu. He was elected from the Saidapet constituency. .

During this period, in order to provide decent living conditions for slum dwellers, the Slum Clearance Board was created. Multi-story buildings were built to accommodate the oppressed people. Some bus service lines were also nationalized.

Justice P.V. Rajamannar Committee which had as members A.L. Mudaliar and P. Chandra Reddy, presented its report on center-state relations. Based on this report, the State Autonomy Resolution on internal governance was subsequently passed by the Legislative Assembly of Tamil Nadu.

On the recommendation of Justice A.K. Rajan's committee, the Hindu Religious endowment Act was amended to allow all eligible members of the community to become priests in Hindu temples. But the Supreme Court invalidated the law for legal and technical reasons in 2015.

One of the biggest benefits Karunanidhi had given to the aided college teachers was the extension of the Pension Scheme after retirement, on par with government college teachers. To relieve heavy vehicle traffic, the Anna Flyover was built and inaugurated on 1st July 1973. It has become a major landmark in Chennai. Another achievement of Karunanidhi was the Chief Minister hoisting India's national flag on Independence Day in state capitals. The Governor's raising of the national flag in the State capitals on Independence Day and Republic Day was a tradition. Karunanidhi thought it was unfair for the Governor to raise the national flag on both occasions. He fought with the Central Government, led by Indira Gandhi, and won the right to hoist the national flag on 15th August 1974. Subsequently, the Chief Ministers of all states raised the national flag on Independence Day in their capitals.

The Emergency time of Karunanidhi,

The Emergency was imposed by Prime Minister Indira Gandhi on 25th June 1975. All fundamental rights of Indian citizens were suspended and she had almost become a dictator. The next day, under the direction of Karunanidhi, the D.M.K. passed a resolution condemning the imposition of the Emergency. Seven months later, on 31st January 1976, his government was ousted from power and Prime Minister, Indira Gandhi imposed the president's rule in Tamil Nadu.³⁰⁷

The imposition of the Emergency by Indira Gandhi in 1975, which repressed dissent through censorship and the indiscriminate arrest of political leaders, aroused great concern for Karunanidhi against the emergency.³⁰⁸

With the innate character of democracy, D.M.K. leader M. Karunanidhi, in power or out of it, had reacted harshly whenever democracy was threatened. Despite being a friend of Indira Gandhi and a reliable ally of the Congress Party, when Indira Gandhi broke democracy by declaring a national emergency in 1975, the D.M.K. remained committed to democracy and fought tooth and nail against the imposition of the Emergency. The fight against the emergency had become a second war for freedom.³⁰⁹

Tamil Nadu was at the forefront under Karunanidhi's leadership. Through deception and threats, D.M.K. was pushed to follow the line of the Central Government, but no force above all could intimidate Karunanidhi. His faith in democracy was and remained firm and unshakable. As a result, D.M.K. leaders such as Murasoli Maran, Arcot Veerasamy, Chitti Babu, Sattur Balakrishnan, and M.K. Stalin with over 500 volunteers were imprisoned under the Maintenance of Internal Security Act (M.I.S.A.). But D.M.K. was able to withstand the repression and faced trials and tribulations. In fact, „M.I.S.A.“ became an honor to be placed before one's name.³¹⁰

In the days of Emergency, Karunanidhi was the only Chief Minister who gave everything to protect citizens' freedoms from state aggression. In a meeting in Madras where Indira Gandhi and Karunanidhi as Chief Minister addressed. Karunanidhi said that he will extend his hands for friendship, but he will raise his voice for rights. Indira Gandhi took offense at these words and sacked his government for opposing the emergency.

However, in 1980, Indira Gandhi herself, expressing her regret for having imposed the emergency and assuring the nation that it would never repeat itself under any circumstances. The D.M.K. under M. Karunanidhi magnanimously renewed its alliance with Congress, forgetting and forgiving the past, as C.N. Annadurai used to state.³¹¹

It was during this period that Rajaji died on 25th December 1972. E.V.R. died on 24th December 1973. K.Kamaraj died on 2nd October 1975. Kalaingar made all arrangements to cremate them.

Karunanidhi's third term of Chiefministership of Tamil Nadu was from 27th January to 30th January 1991. His fourth term of Chiefministership covered the period from 13th May 1996 to 13th May 2001. His last and fifth term of Chiefministership was from 13th May 2006 to 15th May 2011. During his last term, New Secretariat building was inaugurated by the then Prime Minister, Manmohan Singh. Further Anna Centenary Library, an eight storeyed building was inaugurated on 15th September 2010.

Karunanidhi began writing stories and dialogues for films from 1947. „*Rajakumari*“,

„*Marudha Naattu Ilavarasi*“ and „*Mandhira Kumari*“ were his films. In „*Parasakthi*“, (1952), Sivaji Ganesan acted, propagated his progressive views. His films had exciting dialogues. The dialogues of the drama, Socrates in the film of *Raja Rani* and the film „*Manohara*“ improved his image. „*Malaikkallan*“, in which M.G.R. starred, was a successful film. Karunanidhi wrote a story and dialogues for about seventy films.

Karunanidhi had written countless books. It is worth mentioning *Nenjukku Needhi* which was his autobiography and the history of the D.M.K.. *Tholkappiapoonga* is a captivating work on *Tholkappiam*. His commentary on *Thirukkural*, *Kuraloviyam* is an interesting work.³¹² Karunanidhi had made stories and dialogues for several television series and one of these that had attracted all sectors of society was *Ramanujar* in 2016).

Throughout 2017 and until August 2018, Karunanidhi's health was not good. He passed away on 7th August 2018. The next day he was buried next to Anna Samadhi with full honors of state. The whole Tamil world mourned his death.³¹³ His son, M.K.Stalin, Became the President of the D.M.K., led the party and he became the Chief Minister of Tamil Nadu since 7th May 2021

The politics of Tamil Nadu

According to Annadurai, Indian civilization was not one based solely on Brahmin culture, but was an agglomeration of various secular, regional and religious factors. He was against the interpretation of nationalism along religious lines. For him, religion has no role to play in politics. He was in favor of secular democracy and not theocracy. Dravidian separatism plus Indian nationalism was the ideology offered by Annadurai to the politics of Tamil Nadu. His political enemies used to criticize the "Dravida Nadu question" very often. In this regard, Annadurai never went against his principles, but made the necessary changes in policies with reference to changing circumstances. The resolutions he presented at the Salem Justice Party Conference in 1944, his conflict with E.V.R. on the August issue and switched to language- oriented politics in 1963 bandoning racially-oriented politics, he showed his pragmatic approach. This is called customer policy. Consequently, a politician should formulate his policies only according

A prominent figure and a great intellectual leader in Tamil Nadu politics for about thirty years, from the anti-Hindi agitation of 1938, through which he registered his entry into the forefront of politics, until 1969, the year of his death, making all Tamils cry regardless of their political identification. Despite the short period of his administration, from March 1967 to February 1969, he made the people of the Tamil Nadu State believe they were living in a new era.

He was a product of E.V.R. camp which had fought for the self-respect of the Tamils since 1926. He imbibed Western thoughts and delivered them to the Tamils in his style of speech. He condemned society's backwardness and superstitious practices and admired Western life in which science and education played a role in life. At the same time, he was particular in preserving the identity and antiquity of the Tamil language and culture. In short, he wanted to purge politics and for this power had been a weapon in his hands. He was in favor of the improvement of the Tamil language and the due participation of Tamil society in Indian politics. He was a radicalist and a rationalist, but not an extremist. He was Marxist in thought, but Gandhian in approach. Therefore, he renounced the claim of Dravida Nadu when the need arose to renounce the claim.

Political entity by historical compulsions.

He had always been against the imposition of a language on people whose mother tongue was a different language. He considered it a linguistic imperialism. He was in favor of the unity of the Indian states but not of uniformity. He was against the Centre's stepmother attitude towards the provinces. For him, India was a geographical expression transformed into a political entity by historical compulsions. This identity and integrity could be preserved, he said, only through the interdependence of languages, cultures, nationalities and governments of the States and the Centre. For him, language and race were the main factors in determining nationality. He believed that the Hindu religion was a discipline imposed on the people of South India. He was against the second-rate treatment of Tamils in politics and religion. For him, India was not just the Hindi belt, but something else. Indian civilization was not based solely on Brahmin culture, but was an agglomeration of various secular, regional and religious factors. He was against the interpretation of nationalism along the religious lines. He had no consideration for the role of religion in politics. He was in favor of secular democracy and not theocracy.

CONCLUSION

The political career of M. Karunanidhi marked a significant phase in the history of Tamil Nadu, characterized by social reform, industrial development, and a strong commitment to democratic values. From succeeding C. N. Annadurai to leading the state through multiple terms,

Karunanidhi consolidated the ideals of the Dravidian movement while adapting to changing political realities.

His administrations focused on education, welfare of farmers, social justice, and infrastructure development. Landmark initiatives such as the expansion of free education, the formation of the Slum Clearance Board, and major projects like the Anna Flyover reflect his vision for a progressive and inclusive society. His efforts to ensure state autonomy and his resistance during the The Emergency highlight his unwavering faith in democracy.

Even beyond politics, Karunanidhi made immense contributions to Tamil literature, cinema, and culture, leaving a lasting intellectual legacy. His ability to balance regional identity with national integration strengthened Tamil Nadu's role within India.

The broader political philosophy shaped by leaders like Annadurai and carried forward by Karunanidhi emphasized secularism, rationalism, linguistic pride, and social equality. Their ideas transformed Tamil Nadu's political landscape, making it more inclusive and people-oriented.

In conclusion, M. Karunanidhi's life and work stand as a testament to visionary leadership rooted in democratic principles, cultural pride, and social justice, leaving an enduring impact on Tamil Nadu and Indian politics as a whole.

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